

THE VIEWS OF THE FOUNDERS OF TRANSLATION THEORY

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Abstract: In this thesis, translation scholars who contributed to the theory of translation and the role of translation in translation studies were described.

Key words: translation, translation theory, translation studies, linguistic direction.

Recent advancements in translation studies represent some of the newest accomplishments in linguistic inquiry, offering clarifications on translation challenges. The theory of translation not only fosters the evolution of novel linguistic subfields but also facilitates the maturation of intricate linguistic domains. Understanding its theoretical underpinnings is deemed crucial for addressing contemporary issues in both translation and linguistics.

Translation theory stands as a pivotal field, pivotal in addressing the challenges encountered during translation endeavors. It meticulously examines diverse perspectives, experiences, and critical translation methodologies, delving into the very rules governing translation, delineating its fundamental principles, and demarcating their boundaries.

According to Peter Newmark, translation is now used as much to transmit knowledge and to create understanding between groups and nations, as to transmit culture [2, P.10].

The realm of translation theory encompasses a myriad of principles, concepts, and methodologies essential for guiding the translation process across different languages. It entails a comprehensive exploration of linguistic, cultural, and social factors influencing translation practices and the resulting texts. Scholars contribute

diverse theoretical frameworks to elucidate the intricacies of the translation process and analyze translated works. These foundational theories draw from various disciplines, addressing elements such as text analysis, translation norms, and the translator's role. Over the study of history, translation theory has been advanced by numerous scholars. Their significant contributions have profoundly shaped both the theory and practice of translation, continuing to inspire and inform the ongoing scientific exploration within the field of translation studies.

In the 1940s and 1990s, a large group of translators worked effectively in Uzbekistan. The school of translation studies founded by Gaybulla Salomov was established. Among the scientists who carried out scientific activities in the spirit of research, L. Abdullayeva, E. Aznaurova, N. Vladimirova, G. Gafurova, N. Komilov, K. Musayev, Yu. Polatov, M. Rasuliy, V. Rahmonov, S. Salomova, Z.Umarbekova, H.Homidov, A.Hojiahmedov, S.Olimov, Z.Isomiddinov to some extent continued the work of Sanjar Siddiq and focused on the quality of my translation [3, P.16].

Translation studies is a relatively new science, which appeared in the middle of the 20th century. First, in the 40s, a linguistic direction appeared in translation studies. "The essence of this trend was that translation is viewed as a linguistic activity in all cases and in all genres. When interpreting the subject of translation problem in this way, it is necessary to look at the general theory of translation as belonging to linguistics, and to approach the research of translation problems in a linguistic way [1, P.57].

Overall, translation theory offers a structure to comprehend the intricate nature of translation and offers direction to translators in producing precise and impactful translations. This theory encompasses the examination of texts, the extraction of valuable insights from them, the evolution of individual languages, and significant insights into their interrelations. Engaging in the study of translation theory empowers scholars and students to grasp the intricacies of their translation endeavors and advance their scholarly pursuits within the discipline.

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